

Seven Conformers of Neutral Dopamine Revealed in the Gas Phase

*Carlos Cabezas, Isabel Peña, Juan C. López and José L. Alonso**

Grupo de Espectroscopía Molecular (GEM), Edificio Quifima, Laboratorios de Espectroscopia y Bioespectroscopia, Parque Científico UVA, Universidad de Valladolid, 47005 Valladolid, Spain

ABSTRACT The rotational spectrum of neutral dopamine has been investigated for the first time using a combination of Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy with laser ablation. The parameters extracted from the analysis of the spectrum unequivocally identify the existence of seven conformers of dopamine. ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole coupling interactions have been used to determine the orientation of the amino group probing the existence of stabilizing $\text{N-H}\cdots\pi$ interactions for all observed conformers.

TOC GRAPHIC

KEYWORDS

Microwave spectroscopy, laser ablation, conformational analysis, nuclear quadrupole coupling interactions, catecholamines

TEXT Dopamine is a catecholamine which acts as a neurotransmitter and as a hormone in the peripheric and in the central nerve system. It is related to several brain processes such as emotional responses or the ability to experience pleasure and pain.¹⁻³ Like other catecholamines it presents high flexibility leading to a large number of stable conformations. The knowledge of its most favored forms is thus of great interest since shape plays an important role in the key-and-hole recognition process that occur at the receptor site.^{2,3} In recent years, much effort has been devoted to determine the conformational panorama of neurotransmitters in the gas phase.⁴⁻¹¹ However, dopamine has been only studied in crystals by X-Ray diffraction^{12,13} and in solution using nuclear magnetic resonance.^{14,15} In both cases dopamine is stabilized as the N-protonated form $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{OH})_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-NH}_3^+]$ of which the IR spectrum has been also reported.¹⁶ No experimental studies of dopamine in the gas phase, where it adopts a neutral form, have been yet reported probably due to difficulties in its vaporization (m.p. 130 °C). Laser ablation into a supersonic expansion is being used to form neutral biomolecules in the gas phase which are probed by Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy.^{17,18,19} With this LA-MB-FTMW technique we have investigated very recently the neurotransmitter serotonin.¹¹ In this letter we report the first spectroscopic study of neutral dopamine using the aforementioned technique.

Dopamine may exist in various forms differing from each other by the arrangements of the ethylamine side chain and catechol hydroxyl groups. To conduct the analysis of the rotational spectrum we performed a detailed conformational search (see details in Computational and

Experimental section) complementing those already available in the literature.^{20,21,22} For the eighteen low-energy conformers encountered below 1000 cm⁻¹ the essential spectroscopic parameters: rotational constants (A , B and C), nuclear quadrupole coupling constants (χ_{aa} , χ_{bb} , and χ_{cc}) and electric dipole moment components were calculated and are collected in Table 1. According to the predicted values, the rotational spectra for all conformers will show the characteristic pattern of a near prolate asymmetric top with sets of μ_a -type, R-branch transitions separated approximately $B + C$. Thus, wide frequency scans were conducted to search for such rotational transitions and a congested spectrum was observed. Several sets of μ_a -type R-branch lines corresponding to seven different rotamers labeled from I to VII were detected. Apart from the instrumental Doppler doubling, all transitions were observed split into a recognizable hyperfine pattern arising from the ¹⁴N nuclear quadrupole interaction. Dopamine possesses a ¹⁴N nucleus with a non-zero quadrupole moment ($I = 1$) owing to a non-spherical distribution of the nuclear charge, which interacts with the electric field gradient created by the rest of the molecule at the site of this nucleus. The nuclear spin of ¹⁴N nucleus couples to the rotational angular momentum resulting in a hyperfine structure in the rotational spectrum. Initial fits of the μ_a -type transitions and new predictions allowed the measurements of μ_b -type R-branch rotational transitions for all the rotamers. Tables S1–S7 of the Supporting Information show all the measured transitions which were analyzed²³ using the Hamiltonian $H = H_R^{(A)} + H_Q$, where $H_R^{(A)}$ is the A-reduced semirigid rotor Hamiltonian of Watson in the I' representation²⁴ and H_Q accounts for the nuclear quadrupole coupling interaction.²⁵ The fits yielded the experimental values of the rotational constants and the diagonal elements of the nuclear quadrupole coupling tensor, which are listed in Table 2.

Conformational identification of the observed rotamers has been achieved by comparing the experimentally determined molecular properties of Table 2 with those predicted *ab initio* of Table

1. The rotational constants provide information on the mass distribution of each rotamer and are normally conclusive in the conformational assignments. However, as can be seen in Table 2 the differences in the experimental values of the rotational constants for all the rotamers are not large enough to discriminate them. Otherwise, the quadrupole coupling constants are very sensitive to the chemical environment around the ^{14}N nucleus and to the NH_2 group orientation with respect to the principal axis system. In N-containing compounds, they have proven to be of extraordinary value for conformer/tautomer identification, allowing the discrimination between species with very similar molecular shapes, and therefore very similar rotational constants.^{6,8,11,17,18} Comparison of the quadrupole coupling constants of Tables 1 and 2 leads to the identification of the couple of rotamers I/II with the pair of conformers GIc/GId. Nevertheless, the identification of each rotamer as a particular conformer cannot rest only on the quadrupole coupling constants since they have similar values due to the same orientation of the NH_2 group (Figure 1). GIc and GId conformers differ only in the orientation of the hydroxyl groups which produces specific changes in the values of their rotational constants. In going from conformer GIc to conformer GId the predicted changes are $\Delta A = 4$ MHz, $\Delta B = -2$ MHz and $\Delta C = -2$ MHz, in agreement with the changes in the experimental values ($\Delta A=2.491$ MHz, $\Delta B=-1.473$ MHz and $\Delta C=-2.066$ MHz) in going from rotamer I to rotamer II. This allows the definitive identification of rotamers I and II as conformers GIc and GId respectively. Note that this assignment is only possible through the observation of the rotational spectra of both species.

Using the same arguments, rotamers III and IV have been identified as conformers GIa and GIb respectively. They differ from each other in the hydroxyl groups orientation and from species GIc and GId in the relative positions of hydroxyl groups respect to the NH_2 group. Rotamers V and VI can be unambiguously identified as the couple of conformers GIc/GId from the values of the

quadrupole coupling constants. Notice at this point that they differ from the previously assigned conformers in the orientation of the NH₂ group, which is reflected in the dramatic change of the values of the quadrupole coupling constants (see Table 2). Once again, the trend on the variation of the rotational constants allowed the identification of rotamer V as conformer GIIc and rotamer VI as the GII d conformer.

The magnitude of the dipole moment components is correlated with the microwave power needed to optimally polarize the molecules; the higher the dipole moment component, the lower the microwave power needed. It is possible, then, to roughly estimate their magnitude from the optimal microwave power used to polarize the transitions of a particular rotamer. The remaining rotamer VII can be initially identified as one of the conformers of the GIIa/GIIb couple on the basis of the quadrupole coupling constants. However, the conclusive assignment was based on the observation of both μ_a and μ_b -type spectra according to the sizeable values of the dipole moment components predicted *ab initio* (Table 1).

The experimental determination of the ¹⁴N quadrupole coupling constants constitutes an exceptional tool that allows the unequivocal establishment of the orientation of the NH₂ group with respect to the molecular frame. Those constants can be used to deduce the nature of the intramolecular interactions in which this functional group is involved. For this class of compounds, characterized by an alkyl-amine chain attached to an aromatic system, the N–H··· π weak hydrogen bond is one of the leading structural motifs stabilizing the structure as pointed out in previous studies.^{6,11} For dopamine, apart from the hydrogen bond of the catechol ring, the seven conformers are indeed stabilized by a weak NH··· π interaction between the amino group and the high π density sites of the aromatic ring. As occurring in other neurotransmitters^{6,11} these weakly polar intramolecular interactions are the forces which drive the conformational preferences in dopamine.

The relative population trend ($G_{Ia} > G_{Ic} \approx G_{Ib} \approx G_{Id} > G_{IIc} \approx G_{IIb} \approx G_{IId}$) in the supersonic expansion has been estimated by the intensity measurements on selected μ_a -type transitions of each conformer.²⁶ This is in accordance with the predicted values of relative energies for the observed conformers (See Table 1).

The observation of seven conformers for dopamine (Figure 1) in the gas phase reflects a rich conformational behavior for this molecule. These results are in sharp contrast with the conformational reduction claimed for catecholamines⁹, for which the tiny number of observed conformers has been interpreted in terms of the conformational restriction induced by the presence of the catechol ring. Note that the observed conformers for dopamine derive from the forms GI and GII of the analogue molecules 2-phenylethylamine (PEA)⁶ and tyramine.²⁷ At least for dopamine it can be said that the presence of a catechol ring does not restrict significantly the number of its stable conformations since it has a multiplicative effect if we consider the four observed conformers of PEA and tyramine. The present investigation clearly demonstrates that no conformational reduction exists in dopamine. This statement can be extended to noradrenaline and adrenaline for which eight and eleven conformers, respectively, have been observed in their rotational spectra.

Theoretical and Experimental section

The conformational landscape of dopamine was investigated through a systematic variation of the dihedral angles that determine the conformation of the side chain. The only restriction imposed was on the orientation of the catechol OH groups. Just the configurations in which both hydrogen atoms are lying in the plane of the aromatic ring and oriented in the same direction were considered since they favor the formation of a hydrogen bond between both hydroxyl groups. Other possible

orientations were rejected because they were much less favorable²⁸. The eighteen structures found in this way were then fully optimized using the Møller–Plesset second-order perturbation method (MP2) coupled with the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set.²⁹ To label the different conformers of dopamine we have used the same notation employed in previous studies of neurotransmitters.⁶ The labeling G or A correspond to the configuration of the alkyl chain, gauche (G, folded) or anti (A, extended) respectively. The Roman numeral denotes the energy order for the different conformations associated with the rotation of the NH₂ group. A third index (a, b, c and d) denotes the different orientations of catechol OH groups respect to the side chain.

The rotational spectrum of dopamine was investigated by using a LA-MB-FTMW spectrometer³⁰ working in the 4–10 GHz frequency region. The samples were prepared by mixing the powder of neutral dopamine (99%, Interchim) with a small amount of a commercial binder. The mixture was pressed to form cylindrical rods, which were placed in a laser ablation nozzle to be vaporized with the third harmonics of a picosecond Nd:YAG laser (ca. 1 mJ per pulse, 35 ps width pulse). The neutral vaporized molecules were seeded in the carrier gas (Ne: 15 bar) and expanded supersonically between the mirrors of the evacuated Fabry-Pérot microwave resonator creating a molecular beam. A microwave radiation pulse (0.3 μ s) was subsequently applied to cause the macroscopic polarization of the molecules in the beam. The molecular de-excitation signal was collected and Fourier transformed to the frequency domain. The spectrometer has a collinear disposition of the supersonic jet and the microwave resonator axis, which causes each hyperfine component to appear as a Doppler doublet. The transition frequencies are calculated as the arithmetic mean of the Doppler components. The estimated accuracy of the frequency measurements is greater than 3 kHz.

Figure 1. The seven observed conformers of dopamine.

Table 1. Calculated spectroscopic parameters and *ab initio* energies at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory for the eighteen low-energy conformers of dopamine.

	A ^a	B	C	χ_{aa}	χ_{bb}	χ_{cc}	$ \mu_a $	$ \mu_b $	$ \mu_c $	ΔE^b	ΔG^c
GIa	2113	675	580	1.93	-1.79	-0.14	1.5	1.1	0.6	0	0
GIb	2118	675	577	1.85	-1.47	-0.38	0.8	3.4	0.9	126	131
GIc	2168	658	575	0.99	-1.76	0.77	0.9	1.3	0.1	35	54
GI d	2172	656	573	0.95	-1.53	0.58	0.6	3.1	0.1	100	156
GIIa	2132	657	574	-0.76	2.38	-1.62	0.2	2.0	2.3	247	314
GIIb	2122	662	576	-0.62	2.45	-1.83	1.2	2.0	0.0	190	259
GIIc	2137	656	576	-0.02	1.50	-1.48	1.4	2.7	1.5	175	235
GII d	2136	654	575	-0.01	1.57	-1.56	0.5	1.6	0.8	192	223
IIIa	2115	672	540	-3.98	2.01	1.97	3.6	1.7	0.2	596	432
IIIb	2111	671	551	-4.46	2.41	2.05	1.0	2.0	1.3	852	554
IIIc	2291	630	539	-3.00	0.93	2.07	1.3	1.8	0.5	811	584
III d	2286	629	538	-3.16	1.09	2.07	2.7	2.7	0.6	902	670
AIa	2570	549	476	2.71	-1.59	-1.12	1.2	1.1	0.0	532	384
AIb	2561	552	477	2.69	-0.93	-1.76	0.8	3.1	0.8	546	405
AIc	2569	550	477	2.16	-2.80	-0.63	1.0	1.2	0.4	526	276
AI d	2592	546	475	2.17	-1.91	-0.26	0.9	3.0	0.1	586	322
AIIa	2547	548	476	1.73	1.79	-3.55	1.0	1.8	1.0	597	327
AIIb	2547	550	477	1.71	1.85	-3.56	1.3	2.5	1.5	560	362

^a A, B, and C represent the rotational constants in MHz; χ_{aa} , χ_{bb} and χ_{cc} are the diagonal elements of the ¹⁴N nuclear quadrupole coupling tensor in MHz and μ_a , μ_b and μ_c are the electric dipole moment components in D. ^b Relative energies with respect to the global minimum in cm⁻¹. ^c Gibbs energies calculated at 298 K at the MP2/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in cm⁻¹.

Table 2. Experimental rotational parameters for the observed rotamers of dopamine.

	I (GIc)	II (GI d)	III (GIa)	IV (GIb)	V (GIIc)	VI (GII d)	VII (GIIb)
A^a	2192.70023(75) ^d	2195.1912(16)	2129.5962(13)	2136.1705(22)	2170.3939(12)	2168.0178(55)	2130.7139(17)
B	649.98068(10)	648.50802(20)	668.35393(19)	667.00988(18)	647.21814(11)	646.4331(12)	659.32824(12)
C	567.489911(85)	565.42383(23)	571.27207(19)	569.86122(38)	567.35500(16)	566.5753(12)	569.05166(24)
ΔJ	0.0627(10)	0.0543(27)	0.0594(27)	0.0486(43)	0.0647(18)	0.045(10)	0.0613(22)
χ_{aa}	0.702(17)	0.675(21)	1.652(27)	1.653(36)	-0.119(26)	[-0.01] ^e	-0.727(32)
χ_{bb}	-1.305(14)	-1.077(16)	-1.247(22)	-1.149(26)	1.636(19)	1.6196(28)	2.491(24)
χ_{cc}	0.603(14)	0.402(16)	-0.405(22)	-0.504(26)	-1.518(19)	-1.6096(28)	-1.763(24)
σ^b	1.4	1.8	2.1	2.1	1.7	2.0	1.7
N^c	37	27	39	28	33	17	22

^aA, B and C are the rotational constants in MHz; Δ_J is the quartic centrifugal distortion constant in kHz; χ_{aa} , χ_{bb} and χ_{cc} are the diagonal elements of the ¹⁴N nuclear quadrupole coupling tensor in MHz. ^b rms deviation of the fit in kHz. ^c Number of measured transitions. ^d Standard error in parentheses in units of the last digit. ^e Fixed to the *ab initio* value.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. List of measured transitions for all the observed conformers of dopamine, tables of molecular properties predicted *ab initio* for all dopamine conformers and complete reference 29. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: jlalonso@qf.uva.es

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research has been supported by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MICINN) (Projects: CTQ2006-05981/BQU, CTQ2010-19008 and Consolider 2010 CSD2009-00038 Molecular Astrophysics) and Junta de Castilla y León (Excelence Research Group Project: VA070A08).

REFERENCES

- (1) Siegel, G. J. *Basic Neurochemistry: Molecular, Cellular and Medical Aspects*; Elsevier-Academic Press: London, 2006.
- (2) Webster, R. A. *Neurotransmitters, Drugs and the Brain Function*; Wiley: New York, 2001.
- (3) Grace, A. A. *Neuropsychopharmacology - The Fifth Generation of Progress*; Williams & Wilkins: New York, 2002.

- (4) Snoek, L. C.; Van Mourik, T.; Simons, J. P. Neurotransmitters in the Gas Phase: A Computational and Spectroscopic Study of Noradrenaline. *Mol. Phys.* **2003**, *101*, 1239–1248.
- (5) Çarçabal, P.; Snoek, L. C.; Van Mourik, T. A Computational and Spectroscopic Study of the Gas-Phase Conformers of Adrenaline. *Mol. Phys.* **2005**, *103*, 1633–1639.
- (6) López, J. C.; Cortijo, V.; Blanco, S.; Alonso, J. L. Conformational Study of 2-Phenylethylamine by Molecular-Beam Fourier Transform Microwave Spectroscopy. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2007**, *9*, 4521-4527.
- (7) LeGreve T. A.; Baquero E.; Zwier T. S. Infrared and Ultraviolet Spectral Signatures and Conformational Preferences of Jet-Cooled Serotonin. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, *129*, 4028-4037 and references therein.
- (8) Alonso, J. L.; Sanz, M.E.; López, J. C.; Cortijo, V. Conformational Behavior of Norephedrine, Ephedrine, and Pseudoephedrine. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 4320-4326.
- (9) Mitsuda, H; Miyazaki, M.; Nielsen, I. B.; Çarçabal, P; Dedonder, C.; Jouviet, C.; Ishiuchi, S.; Fujii, M. Evidence for Catechol Ring- Induced Conformational Restriction in Neurotransmitters. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, *1*, 1130-1133 and references therein.
- (10) Ishiuchi, S.; Asakawa, T.; Mitsuda, H.; Miyazaki, M.; Chakraborty, S.; Fuvii, M. Gas-Phase Spectroscopy of Synephrine by Laser Desorption Supersonic Jet Technique. *J. Phys Chem. A* **2011**, *115*, 10363–10369.
- (11) Cabezas, C.; Varela, M.; Peña, I.; López, J. C.; Alonso, J. L. The Microwave Spectrum of Neurotransmitter Serotonin. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, *14*, 13618-13623 and references therein.
- (12) Bergin, R.; Carlström, D. The structure of the catecholamines II. The Crystal Structure of Dopamine Hydrochloride. *Acta Cryst.* **1968**, *B24*, 1506-1510.
- (13) Giesecke, J. Refinement of The Structure of Dopamine Hydrochloride. *Acta Cryst.* **1980**, *B36*, 178-181.
- (14) Bustard, T. M.; Egan, R. S. The Conformation of Dopamine Hydrochloride. *Tetrahedron*, **1971**, *27*, 4457-4469.

- (15) Solmajer, P.; Kocjan, D.; Solmajer, T. Conformational Study of Catecholamines in Solution. *Z. Naturforsch C.* **1983**, *38*, 758-762.
- (16) Lagutschenkov, A.; Langer, J.; Berden, G.; Oomens, J.; Dopfer, O. Infrared Spectra of Protonated Neurotransmitters: Dopamine. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2011**, *13*, 2815-2823.
- (17) Alonso, J. L.; Peña, I.; López, J. C.; Vaquero, V. Rotational Spectral Signatures of Four Tautomers of Guanine. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 6141-6143.
- (18) Cabezas, C.; Varela, M.; Peña, I.; Mata, S.; López, J. C.; Alonso, J. L. The Conformational Locking of Asparagine. *Chem. Commun.*, **2012**, *48*, 5934-5936 and references therein.
- (19) Peña, I.; Daly, A. M.; Cabezas, C.; Mata, S.; Bermúdez, C.; Niño, A.; López, J. C.; Grabow, J-U.; Alonso, J. L. Disentangling the Puzzle of Hydrogen Bonding in Vitamin C. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2013**, *4*, 65–69.
- (20) Urban, J. J.; Cronin, C. W.; Roberts, R. R.; Famini, G. R. Conformational Preferences of 2-Phenethylamines. A Computational Study of Substituent and Solvent Effects on the Intramolecular Amine-Aryl Interactions in Charged and Neutral 2-Phenethylamines. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **1997**, *119*, 12292–12299.
- (21) Fausto, R.; Ribeiro, M. J. S.; Pedroso de Lima, J. J. A Molecular Orbital Study on the Conformational Properties of Dopamine [1,2-Benzenediol-4(2-Aminoethyl)] and Dopamine Cation. *J. Mol. Struct.* **1999**, *484*, 181-196.
- (22) Park, S. K.; Lee, N.S.; Lee, S. H. Vibrational analysis of dopamine neutral base based on density functional force field. *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, **2000**, *21*, 959-968.
- (23) Pickett, H. M. The Fitting and Prediction of Vibration-Rotation Spectra with Spin Interactions. *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* **1991**, *148*, 371-377.
- (24) Watson, J.K.G. In *Vibrational Spectra and Structure*; Durig, J.R., Ed., Elsevier: Amsterdam, 1977; Vol. 6, pp 1-89.
- (25) Gordy, W.; Cook, R. L. *Microwave Molecular Spectra*, 3rd Edition, in Weissberger, A. Ed., *Techniques of Chemistry*, Vol. XVIII, John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1984.
- (26) Blanco, S.; Lesarri, A.; López, J. C.; Alonso, J. L. The Gas Phase Structure of Alanine. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **2004**, *126*, 11675-11683.

- (27) Melandri, S.; Maris, A. Intramolecular Hydrogen Bonds and Conformational Properties of Biogenic Amines: A Free-Jet Microwave Study of Tyramine. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2004**, *6*, 2863-2866.
- (28) Van Mourik, T. The Shape of Neurotransmitters in the Gas Phase: A Theoretical Study of Adrenaline, Pseudoadrenaline, and Hydrated Adrenaline. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2004**, *6*, 2827-2837.
- (29) Frisch, M. J.; et al., Gaussian03, Revision B.04, Gaussian, Inc, Pittsburgh, PA, 2003.
- (30) Alonso, J. L.; Pérez, C.; Sanz, M. E.; López, J. C.; Blanco, S. Seven Conformers of L-Threonine in the Gas Phase: A LA-MB-FTMW Study. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2009**, *11*, 617-627 and references therein.